

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

How to interpret this form: This form is to be read and signed by the Researcher. This form is the Researcher’s commitment to ethical research practices. Please make yourself knowledgeable of the PRODIGEES Data Protection Policy, as well as the European Union General Data Protection Regulations (EU-GDPR). Please return this signed commitment to the PRODIGEES Project Manager (Benjamin Stewart: benjamin.stewart@die-gdi.de) and your host supervisor.

Researcher Commitment

I, the Researcher, will perform my research with integrity, upholding the principles of the scientific method and in accordance with all EU and national laws and human rights. Concurrently, I will be objective and keep the safety of myself, my fellow researchers, and the research participants as the utmost priority.

I, the Researcher, will not engage in enterprises which exploit the research, the research participants, the affiliated institutions, nor the PRODIGEES project commercially; this includes but is not limited to commercial advertising, database marketing, and direct marketing of methods or results.

I, the Researcher, will only perform research which is legal by EU and national law. I will only perform legal data transfers of both personal data and research data. When I transfer personal data and research data across borders, I am responsible for confirming that the transfer is legal under EU and national law.

I, the Researcher, have read and agree to the PRODIGEES Data Protection Policy, and I have familiarized myself with the legal guidelines of the European Union General Data Protection Regulations (EU-GDPR).

I, the Researcher, confirm that participating in the PRODIGEES project, and any of the eligible funding received therein, is compatible with any third-party or alternative funding I may receive, including but not limited to stipends, scholarships and salaries from employers or sponsors.*

I, the Researcher, am aware that by breaking any of these affirmations, I risk expulsion from my local research group and the PRODIGEES project. I am also aware that by breaking any of these commitments I am at risk of being prosecuted by local and EU authorities.

Researcher name [printed]

Originating Institution

Signature

Date

* By signing this document, you confirm that you have checked with your employer and/or third-party sponsor and that there are no funding compatibility conflicts with your participation in this EU Horizon 2020 MSCA-RISE project.

